

B-Scan Evaluation of Posterior Segment of Eye in Ocular Blunt Trauma: Epidemiology and Radiological FindingsSaroj Mohanty¹, Amulya Kumar Panda², Savitri Bhagat³, Jagabandhu Barik⁴¹Postgraduate Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, VIMSAR, Burla, Odisha, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, VIMSAR, Burla, Odisha, India³Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, VIMSAR, Burla, Odisha, India⁴Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, VIMSAR, Burla, Odisha, India

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Abstract:

Background: Ocular trauma significantly impairs vision, with blunt trauma often damaging the eye's posterior segment. Effective evaluation is crucial for timely management. B-scan ultrasonography (USG) is a valuable diagnostic tool for assessing posterior segment pathologies, even with opaque media. The study aims to evaluate the epidemiology and radiological findings of posterior segment pathologies in ocular blunt trauma patients using B-scan ultrasonography, focusing on the association of age and occupation with these injuries.

Methods: This cross-sectional study included 180 patients with a history of ocular blunt trauma. Patients underwent B-scan ultrasonography using a GE Logiq S8 XD clear ultrasound machine. Data collected included demographic information, occupation, and detailed sonographic findings. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS software.

Results: The average age of the patients was 35.5 years. Males constituted 68.9% of the cases, with a male-to-female ratio of 2.2:1. Injuries were more common in the left eye (54.4%) than the right eye (36.1%), with 9.4% of cases involving both eyes. Farmers (33.3%) and laborers (28.8%) were the most affected occupational groups. Agriculture-related causes were the most prevalent mode of injury (37.7%). Pathological findings were detected in 61.6% of the cases. Vitreous hemorrhage was the most common pathology (53.3%), followed by retinal detachment (20.5%) and cataract formation (22.7%).

Conclusion: B-scan ultrasonography is an essential tool for diagnosing posterior segment pathologies in ocular blunt trauma. Vitreous hemorrhage was the most frequent finding, often associated with agricultural and heavy object-related injuries. The study highlights the significant role of occupation and environmental factors in ocular injuries, underscoring the need for targeted preventive measures.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and multi-center collaborations are recommended to validate these findings. Implementing preventive strategies in high-risk occupations can reduce the incidence of ocular blunt trauma.

Keywords: Ocular blunt trauma, B-scan ultrasonography, Vitreous hemorrhage, Retinal detachment, Posterior segment pathologies.

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Introduction

Ocular trauma is a major cause of visual impairment and blindness worldwide, with blunt trauma being a major contributing factor. Blunt ocular trauma often results from direct impact to the eye, leading to various degrees of injury to both anterior and posterior segments of the eye. The posterior segment, including the choroid, retina, vitreous, and optic nerve, is particularly susceptible to severe damage, which can result in permanent vision loss if not promptly and accurately diagnosed [1].

The evaluation of posterior segment injuries presents a clinical challenge due to the complex anatomy and limited accessibility for direct

examination. Traditional methods, such as funduscopy, can be hindered by media opacities like corneal edema, hyphema, or vitreous hemorrhage [2]. Hence, imaging modalities play a critical role in the assessment and management of these injuries. B-scan ultrasonography (USG) has emerged as a vital diagnostic tool, offering a non-invasive, real-time evaluation of the posterior segment, even in the presence of opaque media [3].

B-scan ultrasonography utilizes high-frequency sound waves to create detailed images of the eye's internal structures. It is particularly useful for detecting conditions such as vitreous hemorrhage, retinal detachment, choroidal detachment, and

other intraocular pathologies. Its advantages include the ability to provide immediate results, portability, and safety, as it does not involve ionizing radiation. Previous studies have demonstrated its high diagnostic accuracy in identifying posterior segment pathologies following blunt ocular trauma [4].

The study aims to evaluate the epidemiology and radiological findings of posterior segment pathologies in ocular blunt trauma patients using B-scan ultrasonography, focusing on the association of age and occupation with these injuries.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a hospital based cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the outpatient department of ophthalmology at Veer Surendra Sai Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (VSSIMSAR), Burla, Odisha, India, over a span of two years from April 2021 to March 2023. Patients were then referred to the Department of Radiodiagnosis at the same institution for further evaluation.

Study Population

The study included 180 patients with a history of blunt ocular trauma.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with ocular blunt trauma irrespective of age,
2. with a history of ocular blunt trauma within the past two years.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with open globe injuries,
2. with active ocular surface or eyelid infection,
3. with pre-existing non-traumatic posterior segment disorders.

Bias: There was a chance that bias would arise when the study first started, but it was avoided by giving all participants the identical information and hiding the group allocation from the nurses who collected the data.

Equipment: Ultrasound B-scan of both eyes was performed using an 8-15 MHz transducer with a GE Logiq S8 XD clear ultrasound machine.

Figure 1: LOGIQ S8 Xd clear ultrasound machine

Patient Preparation: No specific preparation was required prior to examination as the study was conducted on an emergency basis. Very uncooperative patients, particularly those in the pediatric age group, were studied after administering mild sedation.

Technique of Ophthalmic Ultrasound

- Positioning: The patient was asked to lie supine on the examination table with their eyes closed.
- Procedure: Both eyes were examined through the closed eyelid using a high-frequency linear

transducer. A generous amount of gel was applied over the closed eyelid to improve probe contact.

- B-Mode Imaging: The examination was performed first in B-mode. The focus, gain, and settings were adjusted as needed during the examination to highlight different structures. The globe and optic nerve sheath were visualized by reducing the gain, while increasing the gain enabled the study of the vitreous body contents.

- Doppler Evaluation: Color and pulsed Doppler imaging were used as needed to evaluate vascular

abnormalities, with settings adjusted for low-flow

detection and small gate sizes.

Figure-2: Ultrasound technique. Photograph of a standard examination shows the position of the transducer. Gel should be applied abundantly to allow better contact between the transducer and the eye.

Study Technique

- Scanning Method: The eye was scanned in a neutral position and during gentle eye movements. Axial sections were obtained from the upper to lower poles, and sagittal sections from the temporal to nasal sides. Oblique images were also utilized to achieve a comprehensive 3-D mental image of the ultrasound findings.

- Dynamic Examination: Patients were instructed to move their eyes from side to side and up and down without opening their eyelids. This technique was particularly useful for detecting vitreous diseases and detachments of the posterior vitreous, retina, and choroid.

- Probe Handling: The probe was held in contact with the eyelid without exerting pressure to prevent anterior chamber collapse. This was crucial in ocular trauma cases to avoid rupturing an already injured eye wall.

Evaluation Parameters

During the ultrasound examination, several parameters were meticulously noted to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the posterior segment of the eye. The eyeball was assessed for its size, shape, and position to detect any deviations from normal anatomy. The anterior chamber was evaluated for its depth and any signs of pathology. The iris and angle structures were examined to identify abnormalities that might affect intraocular pressure or indicate trauma.

The lens was scrutinized for its position, shape, and echogenicity, which could reveal dislocations, opacities, or other lens-related issues. The vitreous cavity was observed for the presence of any hemorrhage, detachment, or other pathological changes. The chorioretinal complex was assessed

to detect any signs of retinal detachment, subretinal fluid, or other abnormalities.

The optic nerve was examined to ensure its normal appearance and to detect any signs of swelling or atrophy. The retro orbital tissues were evaluated to identify any signs of trauma or pathological changes extending beyond the globe of the eye. Finally, Doppler evaluation was performed to assess vascular abnormalities, including blood flow irregularities that could indicate conditions such as subretinal cysts or other vascular lesions. This comprehensive set of parameters ensured a detailed and thorough assessment of the posterior segment in patients with ocular blunt trauma.

Safety and Contraindications: Ultrasound is contraindicated if a ruptured globe is suspected, as extrusion of contents may occur. The decision to perform ultrasound was based on clinical judgment, particularly in trauma cases with a high suspicion of extrusion. Color Doppler imaging was employed for detecting and differentiating vascular lesions and complications of infections.

Data Analysis: Data collected included demographic information, occupation, and detailed findings from the B-scan ultrasonography. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software, with descriptive statistics summarizing the data and chi-square tests assessing associations between categorical variables.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 180 patients with a record of ocular blunt trauma were examined. The average age was 35.5 years, with a standard deviation of 16 years. The

youngest patient was 6 years old, and the oldest was 71 years old. The age distribution was as follows: 12 patients (6.6%) were between 1-10 years, 20 patients (11.1%) were between 11-20 years, 47 patients (26.1%) were between 21-30 years, 32 patients (17.7%) were between 31-40

years, 21 patients (11.6%) were between 41-50 years, 37 patients (20.5%) were between 51-60 years, and 11 patients (6.1%) were older than 60 years. Among these patients, 124 (68.9%) were male and 56 (31.1%) were female, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 2.2:1.

Table 1: Age and Gender distribution

Age group (years)	Frequency (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
1-10	12 (6.6%)	8 (6.5%)	4 (7.1%)
11-20	20 (11.1%)	14 (11.3%)	6 (10.7%)
21-30	47 (26.1%)	32 (25.8%)	15 (26.8%)
31-40	32 (17.7%)	22 (17.7%)	10 (17.9%)
41-50	21 (11.6%)	15 (12.1%)	6 (10.7%)
51-60	37 (20.5%)	32 (25.8%)	5 (8.9%)
>60	11 (6.1%)	8 (6.5%)	3 (5.4%)

In terms of the side of injury, 65 patients (36.1%) had trauma to the right eye, 98 patients (54.4%) had trauma to the left eye, and 17 patients (9.4%) had trauma to both eyes. Regarding occupation, the distribution was as follows: 60 patients (33.3%)

were farmers, 24 patients (13.3%) were housewives, 24 patients (13.3%) were students, 52 patients (28.8%) were laborers, and 20 patients (11.1%) were from other professions.

Table 2: Side of Injury

Side of injury	Frequency (%)
Right eye only	65 (36.1%)
Left eye only	98 (54.4%)
Both eye	17 (9.4%)

The mode of injury varied among the patients. Agriculture-related causes were the most prevalent, accounting for 68 cases (37.7%). Heavy objects caused injuries in 33 cases (18.3%), household objects in 29 cases (16%), sports-related injuries in 16 cases (8.9%), physical assault in 14 cases (7.8%), insect-related injuries in 7 cases (3.9%), and unknown objects in 13 cases (7.2%).

Table 3: Occupation Distribution

Occupation	Frequency (%)	Male (%)	Female (%)
Farmer	60 (33.3%)	49 (39.5%)	11 (19.6%)
Housewife	24 (13.3%)	0 (0%)	24 (42.9%)
Student	24 (13.3%)	19 (15.3%)	5 (8.9%)
Labourer	52 (28.8%)	38 (30.6%)	14 (25.0%)
Other	20 (11.1%)	18 (14.5%)	2 (3.6%)

The time of presentation after injury also varied. A majority of the patients, 127 cases (70.5%), presented within one month of injury. Of these, 101 cases (56.1%) presented within 1-14 days and 26 cases (14.4%) within 15-30 days. Eighteen patients (10%) presented within 31-90 days, 21 patients (11.6%) presented within 91-180 days, and 14 patients (7.7%) presented after more than 180 days. Pathological findings were detected in 111 cases (61.6%), while 69 cases (38.3%) revealed no significant abnormalities. Among those with

pathological findings, 76 patients (42.2%) were male, and 35 patients (19.4%) were female. The distribution of pathological findings across different age groups was as follows: 5 cases (4.5%) were between 1-10 years, 13 cases (11.7%) between 11-20 years, 29 cases (26.1%) between 21-30 years, 19 cases (17.1%) between 31-40 years, 11 cases (9.9%) between 41-50 years, 26 cases (23.4%) between 51-60 years, and 8 cases (7.2%) were older than 60 years.

Table 4: Pathological findings

Pathology	Frequency (%)
Vitreous hemorrhage	96 (53.3%)
Posterior vitreous detachment	8 (4.4%)
Retinal detachment	37 (20.5%)
Choroidal detachment	10 (5.5%)
Cataract	41 (22.7%)
Ectopia lentis	8 (4.4%)
Subretinal cysts	6 (3.3%)
Small globe	8 (4.4%)
Subretinal collection/Hemorrhage	4 (2.2%)

The sonological findings revealed a variety of posterior segment pathologies. Vitreous hemorrhage was the most common, detected in 96 cases (53.3%), with a male-to-female ratio of 2.1:1. Posterior vitreous detachment was found in 8 cases (7.2%), with a male-to-female ratio of 3:1. Retinal detachment was detected in 37 cases (20.5%), with a male-to-female ratio of 2.7:1. Choroidal detachment was observed in 10 cases (5.5%), with

an equal distribution between males and females. Cataract formation was noted in 41 cases (22.7%), with a male-to-female ratio of 2.7:1. Ectopia lentis was present in 8 cases (4.4%), all males. Subretinal cysts were found in 6 cases (5.4%), all males. Small globe was noted in 8 cases (7.2%), with a male-to-female ratio of 1:1.7. Subretinal collection/hemorrhage was observed in 4 cases (3.6%), all associated with vitreous hemorrhage.

Table 5: Vitreous Hemorrhage (VH) associations

Association	No. of cases (%)
Agriculture-related objects	30 (31.2%)
Heavy objects	26 (27%)
Household objects	18 (18.7%)
Physical assault	5 (5.2%)
Sports-related injuries	9 (9.3%)
Associated with RD	28(29%)
Associated with cataract	30 (31.2%)
Associated with PVD	8 (8.3%)
Associated with Ectopic lentis	7 (7.3%)
Associated with Small globe	5 (5.2%)
Associated with CD	6 (6.2%)
Associated with Subretinal cysts	1 (1%)

The association of these pathologies with various factors revealed that vitreous hemorrhage was commonly associated with injuries caused by agricultural and heavy objects. Posterior vitreous detachment was mostly found in farmers and laborers. Retinal detachment had a higher prevalence among farmers and laborers. Choroidal detachment was equally distributed among males and females, with agriculture and household objects being common causes. Cataracts were

frequently found in farmers and laborers, and were associated with vitreous hemorrhage, retinal detachment, and other conditions. Ectopia lentis was predominantly seen in males, with agriculture, household, and heavy objects as common causes. Subretinal cysts were seen in males, often associated with vitreous hemorrhage and retinal detachment. Small globe cases were more common in females and were associated with vitreous hemorrhage and choroidal detachment.

Figure 3: Comparative study in a man with anisometropia in long-standing myopia in the right eye. A. Longitudinal US shows the lengthened anteroposterior axis of the right eye, with a pear-shaped posterior pole sacculation known as a staphyloma Compare with the left eye.

Figure 4: Phthisis bulbi in a 42-year-old male farmer with a history of right ocular trauma 5 month back. Axial US image shows a small, crenated, shrunken-looking ocular globe with calcified walls and echogenic material within.

Figure 5: 53-year male farmer with history of blunt ocular trauma by wood, Cataractous lens seen as a echogenic lens.

Figure 6: Partial lens dislocation in a 42-year-old man with a history of ocular trauma 3 months earlier. He developed a post-traumatic cataract.

Figure 7: 29yr male patient with history of ocular trauma by cow horn on left eye 5month back. Axial US image shows the dislocated lens, which lies entirely within the vitreous. The lens is echogenic and swollen (cataractous)

Figure 8: 16 yr. female patient with history of ocular trauma 5day back by furniture. Axial US image shows the completely dislocated lens, which lies entirely within the vitreous just above optic disc.

Figure 9: Vitreous haemorrhage in a 59-year-old male farmer presented 10 days after ocular trauma. At US, thick echogenic material was noted within vitreous. Transverse and longitudinal scanning have been done. Cataractous lens.

Figure 10: Axial US in a 23-year-old male with findings suggestive of posterior vitreous detachment. Note the undulating appearance of the posterior vitreous that is better identified on dynamic scanning. Note the presence of Vitreous Haemorrhage also.

Discussion

This study examined 180 individuals with a history of ocular blunt trauma to evaluate the epidemiology and radiological findings of posterior segment pathologies using B-scan ultrasonography. The mean age was 35.5 years, with a range from 6 to 71 years. The age distribution showed that the largest group was between 21-30 years (26.1%), followed by those aged 51-60 years (20.5%). Males were predominantly affected, accounting for 68.9% of the cases, with a male-to-female ratio of 2.2:1.

In terms of the side of injury, the left eye was more frequently injured (54.4%) compared to the right eye (36.1%), and 9.4% of the patients had bilateral eye injuries. Occupational analysis revealed that farmers (33.3%) and laborers (28.8%) were the most affected groups, highlighting the higher risk associated with outdoor and manual work. Housewives and students each accounted for 13.3% of the cases, while 11.1% were from other professions.

The mode of injury varied, with agriculture-related causes being the most prevalent (37.7%), followed by injuries from heavy objects (18.3%) and household objects (16%). Sports-related injuries (8.9%), physical assaults (7.8%), insect-related injuries (3.9%), and unknown objects (7.2%) were less common.

Most patients (70.5%) presented within one month of injury, with a significant number (56.1%) presenting within the first two weeks. Pathological findings were detected in 61.6% of the cases. Vitreous hemorrhage was the most common pathology, observed in 53.3% of the patients, with a male-to-female ratio of 2.1:1. Posterior vitreous detachment was found in 4.4% of cases, retinal detachment in 20.5%, choroidal detachment in 5.5%, and cataract formation in 22.7%. Ectopia lentis, subretinal cysts, and small globe were each observed in 4.4% of cases, while subretinal collection/hemorrhage was found in 2.2% of cases.

The association of vitreous hemorrhage with various factors revealed that agricultural (31.2%) and heavy objects (27%) were the most common causes. Vitreous hemorrhage was frequently associated with retinal detachment (29%) and cataract formation (31.2%). Posterior vitreous detachment was predominantly seen in farmers and laborers, indicating a link with manual labor. Retinal detachment had a higher prevalence among farmers and laborers as well. Choroidal detachment was evenly distributed between males and females, often caused by agricultural and household objects. Cataract formation was common among farmers and laborers and frequently associated with vitreous hemorrhage and retinal detachment. Ectopia lentis, predominantly seen in males, was commonly associated with agricultural, household,

and heavy objects. Subretinal cysts were often linked with vitreous hemorrhage and retinal detachment, while small globe cases were more frequent in females and associated with vitreous hemorrhage and choroidal detachment.

B-Scan ultrasonography has proven to be an essential diagnostic tool in evaluating the posterior segment of the eye following ocular blunt trauma. This imaging modality offers significant advantages in detecting ocular pathologies that are often not visible during a clinical examination, especially when the ocular media is hazy or opaque.

A cross-sectional study involving 50 patients revealed that B-scan ultrasonography effectively identified posterior segment lesions in cases of ocular blunt trauma. The study reported that retinal detachment was detected in 30% of the cases, and vitreous hemorrhage in 28%, which were significantly higher detection rates compared to clinical examinations [5].

In a comparative study, B-scan ultrasonography and ultrasound biomicroscopy (UBM) were found to provide superior diagnostic information over clinical examination alone. The study included 95 patients and highlighted that vitreous hemorrhage and retinal detachment were the most common findings, each present in 21.1% of cases. These findings underscored the significant role of B-scan USG in detecting posterior segment changes, particularly in cases where clinical examination was impeded by opaque media [6].

In a study, B-scan ultrasonography was used to evaluate posterior segment disorders in individuals with ocular trauma. The research included 100 patients and found that retinal detachment combined with VH was the most common finding, observed in a significant portion of the patients. The study concluded that B-scan USG was crucial for diagnosing posterior segment pathologies, particularly in the presence of opaque ocular media [7].

A specific study focused on pediatric patients with corneo-scleral lacerations demonstrated the effectiveness of B-scan ultrasonography in assessing posterior segment injuries. This prospective study, which included 50 children, emphasized the importance of B-scan USG in managing severe ocular trauma in pediatric cases, highlighting its role in guiding therapeutic decisions and improving outcomes [8].

A comprehensive study at the Armed Forces Institute of Ophthalmology examined 126 patients with ocular trauma and found that B-scan ultrasonography was instrumental in the management of these cases. Vitreous hemorrhage was identified as the most common posterior

segment pathology, occurring in 33.3% of the patients. This study highlighted the crucial role of B-scan USG in detecting hidden posterior segment lesions, which are often missed during clinical examinations [9].

Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the importance of B-scan ultrasonography in the early detection and management of posterior segment pathologies in ocular blunt trauma. The high prevalence of vitreous hemorrhage and its associations with other pathologies highlight the need for prompt and thorough evaluation in affected patients. The study also emphasizes the significant role of occupational and environmental factors in ocular injuries, particularly among farmers and laborers. These insights can help inform preventive strategies and improve clinical outcomes for patients with ocular blunt trauma.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and multi-center collaborations are recommended to validate these findings. Implementing preventive strategies in high-risk occupations can reduce the incidence of ocular blunt trauma.

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List of Abbreviations:

USG: Ultrasonography

VH: Vitreous Hemorrhage

PVD: Posterior Vitreous Detachment

RD: Retinal Detachment

CD: Choroidal Detachment

B-Scan: B-mode Scan

OD: Oculus Dexter (Right Eye)

OS: Oculus Sinister (Left Eye)

OU: Oculus Uterque (Both Eyes)

MHz: Megahertz

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